

1 Inferring Chemical Disequilibrium Biosignatures for Proterozoic
2 Earth-Like Exoplanets

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5 Supplementary Information

Supplementary Figure 1: **Key Parameter Posterior Distributions Derived From Simulated *JWST*/NIRSpec Observations.** **a**, Marginal Posterior distribution of O₂ abundance for the high (green), med. (purple), and low (blue) Proterozoic Earth abundance cases. The vertical black dashed line denotes the input value for the O₂ abundance. Each distribution is inferred from simulated transit observations at noise levels of 5 ppm (un-filled) and 10 ppm (hatched). **b**, Same as **a** but for the CH₄ abundance. **c**, Same as **a** and **b** but for atmospheric temperature. Note the lack of O₂ abundance constraints for all abundance scenarios at both noise levels.

Supplementary Figure 2: **Posterior Distributions for Available Gibbs Free Energy Derived From Simulated *JWST*/NIRSpec Observations.** **a**, Marginal Posterior distribution of the available Gibbs free energy for the high Proterozoic Earth abundance case. The vertical black dashed line denotes the input value for the available Gibbs free energy. Each distribution is inferred from randomly sampled parameter distributions from simulated transit observations at noise levels of 5 ppm (un-filled) and 10 ppm (hatched). **b**, Same as **a** but for the medium abundance case. **c**, Same as **a** but for the low abundance case.

Supplementary Figure 3: **Reflected Light Retrieval Parameters Pertinent to Computing The Available Gibbs Free Energy (Non-essential)**. **a**, Marginal posterior distributions for the high (green), medium (purple), and low (blue) abundance cases for the log abundance of H₂O. Included are distributions for observations simulated at 20 (hatched), 30 (un-filled), and 50 (solid fill) SNR. **b** Marginal Posterior distribution for the log mixing ratio of CO₂. **c** Marginal posterior distributions for the log mixing ratio of O₃. **d**, Marginal posterior distributions for the global surface pressure. Note that each of these parameters are included in the overall Gibbs free energy calculation, but their uncertainties do not substantially impact the overall available Gibbs free energy.

Supplementary Figure 4: **Thermodynamic Calculation for High Proterozoic Earth Case.** Blue bars represent the observed (or input) abundance for each species labeled across the bottom axis. Red bars indicate the equilibrium abundance (calculated from the Gibbs free energy minimization). Yellow bars indicate the absolute value of the difference between the observed and equilibrium abundance for each species. Note that the molecules with a substantially large abundance *and* large difference (i.e., the O₂ and CH₄) are major contributors to the atmospheric chemical disequilibrium signal.

Parameter	Description	Prior
log P ₀ (log Pa)	Surface pressure	[0,8]
T ₀ (K)	Atmospheric temperature	[100,1000]
log O ₂	Molecular oxygen mixing ratio	[-10,0]
log H ₂ O	Water vapor mixing ratio	[-10,0]
log CO ₂	Carbon dioxide mixing ratio	[-10,0]
log O ₃	Ozone mixing ratio	[-10,-2]
log CH ₄	Methane mixing ratio	[-10,0]
log A _s	Surface albedo	[-2,0]
log R _p (log R _⊕)	Planetary Radius	[-1,1]
log M _p (log M _⊕)	Planetary Mass	[-1,2]
log Δp _c (log Pa)	Cloud thickness	[0,8]
log p _t (log Pa)	Cloud top pressure	[0,8]
log τ _c	Cloud optical depth	[-3,3]
log f _c	Cloud fraction	[-3,0]

Supplementary Table 1: List of 14 planetary parameters that were retrieved on in this work using `rfast`. Listed are the parameter names, descriptions, and their corresponding priors.